

Webinar: A shared vision for future data-intensive science in Europe

Opening public consultation of SPECTRUM SRIDA and Technical Blueprint

12 December 2025

Funded by
the European Union

SPECTRUM is funded by the European Union - Grant Agreement Number 101131550

Housekeeping

This webinar will be recorded (excluding Q&A)

Recordings & Presentation will be added to spectrumproject.eu/spectrum-consultation

Questions about the presentation?
Use Q&A box at the bottom

**Technical Issue? Hello's?
Goodbyes?**
Use chat box

Start Recording

Agenda and Speakers

1. SPECTRUM Project overview

Sergio Andreozzi
(EGI Foundation)

2. Technical Blueprint for a compute and data continuum

Eric Wulff
(CERN)

3. Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA)

Xavier Salazar
(EGI Foundation)

Moderator

Valentin Jay
Blanchard
(Neovia
Innovation)

Project overview

Presenter: Sergio Andreozzi (EGI Foundation)

The Exascale Challenge: A New Era for Science

High-Energy Physics (HEP) and Radio Astronomy (RA) are entering the Exascale era, driven by next-generation instruments

High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC)

Square Kilometre Array (SKA)

LOW Frequency ARray (LOFAR) 2.0

Volume

Exabytes of data requiring storage and analysis

Velocity

Data generated at terabytes/petabytes per second, demanding real-time processing

Variety

Complex, heterogeneous data from millions of sensors or thousands of antennas

CHALLENGE

The **computing** for the **next generation of scientific instruments** in High-Energy Physics and Radio Astronomy is an **unsolved problem**

GOAL

Deliver a **Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA)** and a **Technical Blueprint for a European compute and data continuum**.

IMPACT

- **Common vision** on future of infrastructures for data-intensive research
- **Aligning efforts** and reduce fragmentation among initiatives
- **Optimising use** of common digital infrastructures for research

The SPECTRUM Project is funded by the European Union Grant Agreement Number [101131550](https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-opportunities-and-grants-opportunities/european-union-grant-agreement-number-101131550) - **More Info:** spectrumproject.eu

SPECTRUM Strategic Foresight Framework

Current Results

<https://www.spectrumproject.eu/publications>

Community of Practice (CoP)

- Cross-disciplines WGs with experts from HEP, RA and digital infras ([link](#))
- Knowledge Base ([link](#))
- Collaboration platform

D3.1 Community of Practice – Interim report

Status: UNDER EC REVIEW
Dissemination Level: Public

Current Working Groups

- **WG1: Data Management and Access**
- **WG2: Workflow management and organization**
- **WG3: Compute Environment**
- **WG4: SW tools**
- **WG5: Scientific Use cases**
- **WG6: Facilities**

Compendium of Science Use Cases (14)

- From science case to technical challenges, requirements, gaps
- Both technical and policy aspects

D5.1 Representative use cases: analysis and alignment

Status: UNDER EC REVIEW
Dissemination Level: Public

- **High Energy Physics (6)**
- **Radio Astronomy (5)**
- **Chemistry (1)**
- **Meteorological Science (1)**
- **Neuroscience (1)**

Current Results

<https://www.spectrumproject.eu/publications>

Access Policies Recommendations

- Existing access policies across the continuum
- Development of recommendation for Interoperable access

Landscape Analysis

- Existing approaches, services, technical solutions and policies for the federation of data and compute infrastructures

Formulating the Final Results

Technology Track

Capability
Mapping

Technology
Assessment

Capability
Alignment

Technical Blueprint

Strategic Track

Priority
Areas

Investment
Areas

Policy
alignment

SRIDA
(Strategic Research,
Innovation and
Deployment Agenda)

A Technical Blueprint for a European Compute and Data Continuum

Presenter: Eric Wulff (CERN)

Goals and context within SPECTRUM

Goals of the Technical Blueprint:

- Define **key capabilities** for an interoperable compute and data ecosystem
- Integrate **scientific, technical, and policy requirements** from the High Energy Physics (HEP) and Radio Astronomy (RA) Communities
- Provide **clear and actionable recommendations** for future e-infrastructure design and research funding programmes

Builds on previous work within SPECTRUM:

- Community of Practice (CoP) insights and survey findings
- Use cases, access policies, infrastructure landscape, and gap analysis
- Strategic Research, Innovation & Deployment Agenda (SRIDA)

Key priorities: interfaces, co-design, portability, data federation, workflows, AAI/security, AI/ML, and long-term provisioning.

Outcome: a set of actionable technical and policy recommendations for Europe.

Leadership and Timeline

Editorial team

Eric Wulff
(CERN)

Maria Girone
(CERN)

Jeff Wagg
(CNRS)

Publication timeline

Draft
Technical Blueprint for
Compute & Data Continuum

12.2025
(public draft)

Final
Technical Blueprint for
Compute & Data Continuum

Q2 2026
(final)

Technical Blueprint ToC

1. Introduction
2. Preliminary work
 - a. The SPECTRUM CoP
 - b. Use cases
 - c. Landscape analysis
 - d. Access policy recommendations
3. Sustainability
4. Technical Activities and Recommended Actions
5. Conclusion
6. Annex: Capability map for the compute and data continuum

Key capabilities

Technical Activities and Recommended Actions (1/3)

ACTIVITY	DESCRIPTION	ACTIONS
01 Standardization of interfaces	Fragmented APIs and job-submission interfaces hinder site integration and multi-site workflows	Develop and adopt common interfaces, metadata standards, and portability layers aligned with the EuroHPC Federation Platform, enabling seamless execution across computing sites.
02 Infrastructure Co-design	Early HEP/RA involvement in infrastructure design is essential	Engage EuroHPC/national programs for “strategic access.” Represent HEP/RA requirements in early system design (e.g. express need for double precision compute).
03 Software Portability & Maintenance	Codes tuned for CPUs are not optimized for GPUs, FPGAs, or emerging hardware	Review codebases for accelerator readiness. Fund pilot porting projects using portable frameworks.

Technical Activities and Recommended Actions (2/3)

ACTIVITY	DESCRIPTION	ACTIONS
04 Data Management & Network Performance	Lack of long-term storage and limited bandwidth to compute sites constrain scalable data workflows; standard, high-throughput data transfer solutions required	Run joint SRCNet-WLCG-HPC data challenges.
05 Workflow Adaptation & Optimization	Lack of a standardized, production-ready integration layer that allows existing workflow systems to interface seamlessly with site schedulers and policies	Connect existing workflow systems to HPC resource managers for native submission and monitoring, including end-to-end orchestration, and provenance capture.
06 Security & AAI	Multiple incompatible authentication and authorization systems hinders cross-continuum access	Establish a federated AAI framework allowing users to authenticate once and access multiple sites securely, with consistent authorization policies. Harmonize site authorization to accept federated identities and allow for service accounts.

Technical Activities and Recommended Actions (3/3)

ACTIVITY

DESCRIPTION

ACTIONS

07

AI/ML Integration & Computational trends

Rapid growth in AI workloads and hardware requires strategic software refactoring and skills development. Low-precision AI-optimized hardware conflicts with double-precision requirements for (parts of) of HEP/RA

Integrate distributed AI/ML services (training, inference, model repositories) directly into the continuum to accelerate data-driven discovery. Engage HEP and RA communities in HPC co-design processes to influence system architecture, ensuring sustained double-precision performance alongside AI-optimized capabilities. Identify and fund ML-suitable tasks. Train domain scientists in ML.

08

Longer-term Resource Provisioning & Operational Sustainability

Short-term resource allocations hinders long-term viability

Adopt multi-year resource-allocation frameworks. Launch CSA to propose renewable allocation models aligned with experiment lifecycles.

Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA)

Presenter: Xavier Salazar (EGI Foundation)

Leadership and Timeline

Editorial team

Sergio Andreozzi
(EGI)

Xavier Salazar
(EGI)

Publication timeline

Draft
Strategic Research
Innovation & Deployment
Agenda (SRIDA)

12.2025
(public draft)

Final
Strategic Research
Innovation & Deployment
Agenda (SRIDA)

Q2 2026
(final)

1. Introduction

- Purpose and Scope
- Vision and Strategic Goals
- Target Audience

2. Integrated Strategic Foresight Framework and Methodology

3. Strategic Context and Trends

- European Context
- The Evolving Landscape

4. Strategic Priorities

- 4 pillars, 13 priorities

5. Investment Areas

6. Multi-Annual Roadmap

7. Conclusion

8. References

Annexes

- Annex A: Priorities
- Annex B: Priority Description Template
- Annex C: Priority Evidence and Validation

Strategic Pillars of the European Compute & Data Continuum for Research

Template for Describing Priorities

Strategic Rationale and Evidence Base (max 1 page)	
<i>Establish WHY this priority matters for European research infrastructure</i>	
Strategic importance	One-paragraph explanation of why this priority is essential for SPECTRUM's vision and European research competitiveness
Current State	Brief description of existing capabilities and identified gaps in European landscape
Community Evidence	For technical priorities, reference to the SPECTRUM Technical Blueprint (in particular mention the gaps/requirements in Section 2.5); reference to other relevant documents also possible
Technical Foundation	Reference to supporting SPECTRUM Compute and Data Continuum capabilities
European Alignment	Connection to broader European strategies (EOSC, EuroHPC, ESFRI, Digital Decade)

Target Outcomes and Impact Assessment (max 0.5 page)	
<i>Define WHAT success looks like through capability-focused outcomes and realistic progress indicators</i>	
Strategic Outcomes	Capability statements describing what will be achieved
Success Indicator	Qualitative measures showing progress toward outcomes
European Impact	Contribution to European research competitiveness and strategic objectives

Implementation Pathway and Stakeholder Roles (section 6, max 1 page)	
<i>Show HOW the priority will be achieved and WHO is responsible for implementation</i>	
Implementation Phases	Short-term, medium-term, and long-term actions
Stakeholder Roles	Stakeholder group responsibilities and benefits
Resource Needs	Investment dimensions, intensity levels, and funding alignment
Critical Dependencies	Key prerequisites and coordination requirements

Pillar 1: Policy, Trust & Governance

PRIORITY	ADDRESSES	DELIVERS
P01 Cross-Infrastructure Governance	Governance fragmentation: thematic RIs and pan-European infrastructures lack systematic coordination	Structured coordination mechanisms connecting scientific communities with infrastructure providers (e.g. coordination forum)
P02 Federated Resource Allocation	Short-term allocation cycles incompatible with multi-decade research infrastructure programmes	Multi-year strategic allocations aligned with research infrastructure timelines
P03 Federated Identity & Trust	Multiple authentication barriers blocking seamless access and automated workflows	Seamless federated authentication; Automated long-running workflows

Pillar 2: Architecture & Interoperability

PRIORITY	ADDRESSES	DELIVERS
P04 Heterogeneous Computing Integration	Growing heterogeneity of CPU, GPU and accelerator resources across federated sites	Unified interfaces enabling seamless workflow execution across HPC, HTC and Cloud
P05 Data Management & Transport	Exabyte-scale data volumes requiring coordinated federation across scientific domains	Federated FAIR data management with automated large-scale data movement across HTC, HPC, and Cloud
P06 Orchestration & Workflows	Multiple workflow systems with limited cross-facility interoperability and resilience	Interoperable workflow orchestration with provenance tracking across infrastructures

Pillar 3: Software & Science Enablers

PRIORITY	ADDRESSES	DELIVERS
P07 AI/ML	Transformative AI potential not yet systematically integrated into production workflows	Production deployment with training infrastructure, distributed inference, and FAIR model registries
P08 Software Portability	Proprietary software ecosystems limiting portability and hardware flexibility	Deploy portable frameworks enabling cross-platform execution
P09 Open Science & Reproducibility	Multi-decade experimental timescales with evolving software environments	Analyses preserved in re-executable form with full provenance
P10 Software Sustainability	Fragmented funding threatening long-term software preservation and availability	Open Science software repositories with software management plans

Pillar 4: Human Capital & Responsibility

PRIORITY	ADDRESSES	DELIVERS
P11 Community Collaboration	Inconsistent co-design between scientific communities and infrastructure providers	Permanent coordination mechanisms with structured community feedback loops
P12 Environmental Sustainability	Growing environmental impact requiring lifecycle-aware infrastructure approach	Sustainability metrics (PUE/CUE), HEPscore/watt procurement and extended hardware lifetime
P13 Skills, Careers & Training	Inadequate career recognition driving skilled personnel to industry	Established Research Software Engineer (RSE) career paths with competitive recognition and salaries

Conclusion and Next Steps

Presenter: Valentin Jay Blanchard
(Neovia Innovation)

Next steps

Help shape the SRIDA and Technical Blueprint

Join the consultation process

By following this link, you can access a survey that enables you to share your feedback with us.

The survey includes direct access to the draft versions of both the SRIDA and the Technical Blueprint, and its length adapts to the time you have at your disposal.

Your input is essential to help shape the final documents.

The consultation will close on 31 January 2026.

spectrumproject.eu/spectrum-consultation

Brussels, Belgium

June 3rd 2026

A shared vision for the future of data-intensive science in Europe

SPECTRUM FINAL RESULTS

spectrumproject.eu

Stop Recording

Thank you! Questions?

Funded by
the European Union

SPECTRUM is funded by the European Union
- Grant Agreement Number 101131550